

Table 3.5: Baseline studies selected for the RSL.

ID	Title	Ref.	Year	RQ
E1	A taxonomy for mining and classifying privacy requirements in issue reports	[13]	2023	RQ.1 and RQ.2
E2	The CCPA and the GDPR Are Not the Same: Why You Should Understand Both	[29]	2021	RQ.1
E3	Comparing Data Protection Regulation Models of the EU and the US: Which One Is More Preferred by the Society?	[47]	2022	RQ.1
E4	Comparative Analysis of Personal Data Regulations in Brazil and the European Union (LGPD AND GDPR) and their Respective Enforcement Instruments	[40]	2021	RQ.1
E5	GDPR and LGPD: comparative study	[36]	2021	RQ.1 and RQ.2
E6	Understanding Philippine National Agency's Commitment on Data Privacy Act of 2012: A Case Study Perspective	[67]	2018	RQ.2
E7	Privacy Legislation as Business Risks: How GDPR and CCPA are Represented in Technology Companies' Investment Risk Disclosures	[68]	2023	RQ.1 and RQ.2
E8	Understanding Ethics, Privacy, and Regulations in Smart Video Surveillance for Public Safety	[45]	2022	RQ.1
E9	Agile Teams' Perception in Privacy Requirements Elicitation: LGPD's compliance in Brazil	[69]	2021	RQ.1 and RQ.2
E10	Guidelines adopted by agile teams in privacy requirements elicitation after the Brazilian general data protection law (LGPD) implementation	[18]	2022	RQ.1 and RQ.2
E11	A systematic study on the impact of GDPR compliance on Organizations	[4]	2023	RQ.2
E12	The GDPR Compliance and Access Control Systems: Challenges and Research Opportunities	[70]	2022	RQ.2
E13	Are We There Yet?: Understanding the Challenges Faced in Complying with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)	[15]	2018	RQ.2
E14	The Proposed American Data Privacy and Protection Act in Comparison with GDPR	[21]	2022	RQ.1
E15	A comparative analysis of personal data protection regulations between the EU and China	[71]	2020	RQ.1

Table 3.6: Studies selected from snowball.

ID	Title	Ref.	Year	RQ
E16	"The Grace Period Has Ended": An Approach to Operationalize GDPR Requirements	[72]	2018	RQ.2
E17	Privacy Laws and Privacy by Design Schemes for the Internet of Things: A Developer's Perspective	[44]	2021	RQ.1 and RQ.2
E18	The Changing Wind of Data Privacy Law: A Comparative Study of the European Union's General Data Protection Regulation and the 2018 California Consumer Privacy Act	[73]	2019	RQ.1
E19	Why you should care about GDPR in IoT Enterprises & Solutions	[74]	2021	RQ.2
E20	It's all fun and games, and some legalese: data protection implications for increasing cyber-skills of employees through games	[75]	2018	RQ.2
E21	Towards privacy compliance: A design science study in a small organization	[41]	2022	RQ.2
E22	The ethics of facial recognition technologies, surveillance, and accountability in an age of artificial intelligence: a comparative analysis of US, EU, and UK regulatory frameworks	[76]	2022	RQ.1
E23	Using MCDA for selecting criteria of LGPD compliant personal data security	[77]	2020	RQ.2
E24	I'm all ears! Listening to software developers on putting GDPR principles into software development practice	[78]	2021	RQ.2
E25	A comparative analysis between General Data Protection Regulations and California Consumer Privacy Act	[46]	2023	RQ.1
E26	We Are Not There Yet: The Implications of Insufficient Knowledge Management for Organizational Compliance	[17]	2023	RQ.2
E27	A survey on solutions to support developers in privacy-preserving IoT development	[79]	2022	RQ.2
E28	Perceptions of ICT Practitioners Regarding Software Privacy	[43]	2020	RQ.1 and RQ.2
E29	GDPR Compliance in the Context of Continuous Integration	[80]	2020	RQ.2
E30	Information security frameworks for assisting GDPR compliance in banking industry	[81]	2020	RQ.2
E31	Toward Data Protection by Design: Assessing the Current State of GDPR Disclosure in Web Applications	[82]	2023	RQ.2
E32	Challenges Regarding the Compliance with the General Data Protection Law by Brazilian Organizations: A Survey	[83]	2021	RQ.1 and RQ.2
E33	The benefits and challenges of general data protection regulation for the information technology sector	[84]	2019	RQ.2
E34	A Framework for GDPR Compliance for Small- and Medium-Sized Enterprises	[85]	2019	RQ.2
E35	Making Sense of the General Data Protection Regulation - Four Categories of Personal Data Access Challenges	[86]	2019	RQ.2
E36	Diagnostic of Data Processing by Brazilian Organizations - A Low Compliance Issue	[87]	2021	RQ.2
E37	"Those things are written by lawyers, and programmers are reading that." Mapping the Communication Gap Between Software Developers and Privacy Experts	[88]	2024	RQ.2
E38	On Understanding How Developers Perceive and Interpret Privacy Requirements Research Preview	[89]	2020	RQ.2
E39	Privacy Champions in Software Teams: Understanding Their Motivations, Strategies, and Challenges	[90]	2021	RQ.2
E40	GDPR Compliance in SMEs: There is much to be done	[91]	2018	RQ.2
E41	Ensuring Privacy in the Application of the Brazilian General Data Protection Law (LGPD)	[22]	2022	RQ.2
E42	IoT Security and Privacy Challenges from the Developer Perspective	[92]	2023	RQ.2
E43	Privacy Compliance in Software Development: A Guide to Implementing the LGPD Principles	[7]	2023	RQ.1 and RQ.2
E44	Data Protection Officers' Perspectives on Privacy Challenges in Digital Ecosystems	[93]	2022	RQ.2
E45	"It may be a pain in the backside but..." Insights into the resilience of business after GDPR	[94]	2022	RQ.2
E46	The Critical Success Factors of GDPR Implementation: A Systematic Literature Review	[95]	2019	RQ.2
E47	A review of information privacy laws and standards for secure digital ecosystems	[49]	2018	RQ.1 and RQ.2
E48	The General Data Protection Regulation in Financial Services Industries: How Do Companies Approach the Implementation of the GDPR and What Can We Learn From Their Approaches?	[96]	2020	RQ.2
E49	A Narrative Review of Factors Affecting the Implementation of Privacy and Security Practices in Software Development	[60]	2023	RQ.2
E50	Developers Say the Darndest Things: Privacy Compliance Processes Followed by Developers of Child-Directed Apps	[37]	2022	RQ.1 and RQ.2
E51	A Review of GDPR Impacts on Information Security	[97]	2022	RQ.2
E52	Navigating the Data Avalanche: Towards Supporting Developers in Developing Privacy-Friendly Children's Apps	[16]	2023	RQ.2

Table 3.6: Studies selected from snowball.

E53	"Money makes the world go around": Identifying Barriers to Better Privacy in Children's Apps From Developers' Perspectives	[98]	2021	RQ.2
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